

SIGNIFICANCE OF DIAGNOSTIC TRACKS

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Abstract: Diagnostic tasks are to check the operation and correct operation of the object in question and to find defects that disrupt its correct operation. Determining these tasks, firstly, implies the direct or indirect determination of the type of possible defects, and secondly, the existence of formalized methods of creating diagnostic algorithms, the implementation of which provides the identification of a certain type of defects with the required completeness or the search for the latter.

Key words: Diagnostics, methodologically based system, highway, technical level, mobile devices, modern laboratories, test stands

The tasks of diagnostics are as follows: checking the serviceability and correct operation of the object in question and looking for defects that destroy them. A methodologically based system of data collection and analysis in highway diagnostics or technical and operational assessment of highways is inextricably linked with the organization of all road works.

Diagnostics is the process of collecting and analyzing information about the technical and operational condition of the road or its individual object. Diagnostic information previously received it allows to evaluate the project decisions made, to identify the shortcomings made during the construction, to determine the optimal ways to improve the maintenance and repair technology, to choose the most economical methods of managing the work of highways. Initially, assessment of the quality of the roads was carried out by visual methods, measurement of technical and operational conditions of the road was carried out using the simplest tools and

devices. Currently, as the highway network has developed, the level of mechanization of their construction, maintenance and repair has increased, the methods of controlling the technological processes and operational qualities of road structures have been further improved. Today, road diagnostics includes the strength and reliability of road surfaces, the smoothness, roughness and quality of road surfaces, road engineering, road equipment and architecture regulation, ecology and road safety, as well as road quality management system, technology for their maintenance and repair and covers a set of theoretical rules for the organization of work.

World practice shows that technical and automated tools, mobile devices, modern laboratories, test stands, etc. are widely used. The regularity of collecting information about the condition of roads and the systematicity of its processing allow to have quick information for making management decisions on the rational use of material and financial resources.

The purpose of diagnostics of highways:

- * determining the current technical condition of the road;
- * forecasting the technical condition of the road;
- * to determine the causes of road defects.

Diagnostics of the state of transport and use solves the following tasks:

- collecting unbiased information about the state of traffic and technical use of highways;
- assessment of the traffic condition of the roads with the identification of sections requiring repair and determination of the reasons for this inconsistency;
- development of recommendations for forecasting changes in the condition of highways and improving their traffic conditions, determining types and volumes of work;
- road works, taking into account full and limited funding planning;

- creation of an automated bank of road information, which includes processing, storage and transmission of information about the state of transport and use of the highway network.

The issue of optimal management of the road network within the existing means is the most pressing issue. This problem helps to solve the diagnosis of roads, which allows to assess the state of the road network, determine the need for funds for repair, and optimal distribution of funds.

Road diagnostics is the basis of the road condition management system, including road maintenance, repair and reconstruction, road work programs planning, distribution and use of funds allocated for optimization.

Therefore, the goal of diagnosing and evaluating the condition of highways is to obtain complete, objective and reliable information about the transport and operational status of roads, their working conditions, and the level of compliance of their parameters and characteristics with road safety requirements. The results of diagnostics and assessment of road conditions should serve as a reliable information base for solving management tasks at two levels:- determination and assessment of the technical level of highways, transport-operational condition, consumption characteristics;

- a road based on the rational use of financial resources and material and technical resources network status management.

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